

SHORT COMMUNICATION **OPEN ACCESS**

Biological Control of *Echinothrips americanus* Morgan (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) in Sweet Pepper Using the Predatory Thrips *Franklinothrips vespiformis* Crawford (Thysanoptera: Aeolothripidae)

Niel Verachtert

R&D Department, Biobest Group N.V., Westerlo, Belgium

Correspondence: Apostolos Pekas (tolis@biobest.be)

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ABSTRACT

Echinothrips americanus Morgan (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), also known as poinsettia thrips, has invaded several parts of the world becoming an important pest in many vegetable and ornamental crops. While biological control methods using predatory mites and bugs have been effective against flower-dwelling thrips, they have shown limited success against leaf-dwelling thrips like *E. americanus*. *Franklinothrips vespiformis* Crawford (Thysanoptera: Aeolothripidae) is a leaf-dwelling predatory thrips that may offer a more effective solution due to its overlapping habitat with *E. americanus* which increases the likelihood of predator-prey interactions. This study aimed to evaluate the potential of *F. vespiformis* for controlling *E. americanus* populations in sweet pepper under greenhouse conditions. We also investigated whether supplementing the releases of the predator with *Artemia franciscana* Kellogg (Branchiopoda: Artemiidae) cysts would enhance the pest control efficacy of *F. vespiformis*. Our results showed a 93% decrease in the total *E. americanus* population with releases of *F. vespiformis* alone and a 98% decrease when the releases of *F. vespiformis* were supplemented with *A. franciscana* cysts, both of which were statistically significant compared to the control treatment. There was no significant difference between the two *F. vespiformis* treatments. Similarly, the abundance of both adults and immature stages of *E. americanus* was significantly reduced in the presence of *F. vespiformis*, regardless of the addition of supplementary food. Overall, these findings highlight the potential of *F. vespiformis* for the biological control of *E. americanus* and probably other leaf-dwelling thrip pests in sweet pepper.

1 | Introduction

Echinothrips americanus Morgan (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), also known as poinsettia thrips, is a North American species that has invaded several parts of the world, including countries in Europe (such as Belgium, the Netherlands, the UK and others) and Asia (including areas of China, Japan and others) becoming an important pest in many vegetable and ornamental crops (Mouratidis et al. 2022). *Echinothrips americanus* is

present on older leaves of the plant canopy in contrast with other major thrips pests such as *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) which preferably reside in narrow spaces in buds and flowers (Ghasemzadeh, Leman, and Messelink 2017; Mouratidis et al. 2022).

Predatory mites (Acari: Phytoseiidae) and predatory bugs (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) are commonly used for the biological control of flowering-dwelling thrips species but their capacity to

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control leaf-dwelling thrips often falls short of expectations. For instance, the effectiveness of predatory mites such as *Amblyseius swirskii* Athias-Henriot and *Amblydromalus limonicus* (Garman and McGregor) (Acari: Phytoseiidae) against *E. americanus* has been limited due to differences in habitat preferences and the size difference between the predatory mites and older instars of *E. americanus*, which makes it more difficult for the mites to effectively prey on them (Ghasemzadeh, Leman, and Messelink 2017; Vangansbeke et al. 2023). While *E. americanus* is a high-quality food for anthocorid predators such as *Orius laevigatus* (Fieber) and *O. majusculus* (Reuter) (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) (Mouratidis et al. 2022), their preference for flowers, where they feed on pollen, may compromise their efficacy against leaf-dwelling thrips pests. Additionally, although zoophytophagous predatory mirids (Hemiptera: Miridae) could be an option for the control of *E. americanus*, the plant damage they may cause is a concern, especially in ornamental crops (Leman et al. 2020).

Franklinothrips vespiformis Crawford (Thysanoptera: Aeolothripidae) is a leaf-dwelling predatory thrips that may offer a more effective solution due to its overlapping habitat with *E. americanus* and other leaf-dwelling thrips. Previous research has shown the predatory efficiency of *F. vespiformis* against *E. americanus* and also pests such as whiteflies (Schoeller, McKenzie, and Osborne 2022; Schoeller et al. 2024). Interestingly, supplementation of *F. vespiformis* with *Artemia franciscana* Kellogg (Branchiopoda: Artemiidae) cysts resulted in better control of *E. americanus* in lima beans making it a suitable candidate for inclusion in Integrated Pest Management (IPM) programs against *E. americanus* (Schoeller, McKenzie, and Osborne 2022).

We conducted a greenhouse study to investigate the potential of *F. vespiformis* to control *E. americanus* in sweet pepper. We also investigated whether supplementing the releases of the predator with *A. franciscana* cysts would enhance the pest control efficacy of *F. vespiformis*.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Plants and Insects

The materials and experimental design were similar to those described in Pekas et al. (2020). The experiments were performed in a greenhouse at the GreenLab facilities of Biobest N.V. in Westerlo (Belgium). Temperature and humidity were recorded throughout the experiments (Halveon T Stream MU, HALVEON SAGL, Switzerland). Sweet pepper plants, cultivar IDS (Rijk Zwaan), were grown from seeds sown in tray cells and subsequently transplanted in plastic pots (30 cm diameter) filled with potting soil (50% black + 50% white peat) (Greenyard, The Netherlands). A rearing of *E. americanus* was established on the same sweet pepper variety for multiple generations. *Franklinothrips vespiformis* adults used in the experiments were obtained from the stock colony of Biobest and were between 2 and 4 days old.

2.2 | Greenhouse Experiment

This experiment was conducted from October 26, 2022 until January 3, 2023. The average (\pm SE) temperature and relative

humidity (RH) were $17.3^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.04^{\circ}\text{C}$ (min 9.1°C ; max 35.0°C) and $68.1\% \pm 0.14\%$ RH (min 22.5%; max 93%), respectively. The experimental walk-in cages were 1.8 m wide 2.5 m long 2 m high, covered with thrips-proof screen net and a double door with zipper entrance and aligned in two rows of eight and four cages, respectively. Supplemental lighting was provided by high-pressure sodium lamps (HPS) (Phillips MASTER SON-T Agro, 400 W). Four lamps were positioned above each row of walk-in cages and turned on from 5 am to 4 pm daily. Eight sweet pepper plants (1.45 m high, without flowers) were placed at a 0.5×0.5 m grid in every cage. On October 26, we transferred with a fine hairbrush on a marked (with a ribbon) leaf in the middle of the plant, 10 *E. americanus* adults per plant in all cages. On November 17, three cages (= replicates) were used to release 10 adults of *F. vespiformis* per plant another three cages were to release 10 adult *F. vespiformis* per plant in combination with 0.1 g of *A. franciscana* cysts per plant, and three cages to supply 0.1 g of *A. franciscana* cysts per plant to *E. americanus*. As a control, we used three additional cages containing sweet pepper plants infested with 10 *E. americanus* per plant. The *A. franciscana* cysts were sprinkled with a small spoon over the plants. Each treatment was replicated three times, and the resulting 12 experimental cages were distributed in a randomised complete block design. Two more applications of *A. franciscana* took place on December 2 and 14. On November 24, we released another 10 adult *F. vespiformis* per plant.

3 | Statistical Analyses

We employed generalised linear mixed models using the *glmer* function from the *lme4* package (Bates et al. 2015) to analyse the effects of treatments on the various response variables. Treatment was included as the fixed factor and replicate (cage) nested within treatment and assessment date were included as random factors. The dependent variables were the 'Total *E. americanus*' (i.e., larvae + pupae + adults) or each instar separately (adults, pupae or larvae). Each model was fitted using a Poisson distribution. Estimated marginal means (EMMs) for accurate comparisons among treatments were obtained using the *emmeans* package (Lenth 2024). In all analyses, when significant effects were found the *glht* function from the *multcomp* package was used to perform Tukey tests for post hoc pairwise comparisons (Hothorn, Bretz, and Westfall 2008). All statistical analyses were carried out in R v.3.5.1. (R Core Team 2021).

4 | Results

One of the cages with the *F. vespiformis* treatment had to be discarded from the analyses because the plants were infested with aphids. At the end of the assessments, the total *E. americanus* population differed significantly among treatments ($\chi^2 = 74.02$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.0001$) (Figure 1A). The *E. americanus* population was reduced by 93% (mean \pm SE, 53.0 ± 33.0) and 98% (13.6 ± 0.8) in the *F. vespiformis* ($z = 4.98$, $p < 0.0001$) and *F. vespiformis* with *A. franciscana* cyst treatments ($z = 6.79$, $p < 0.0001$), respectively, compared to the control (740.3 ± 126.0). The population of *E. americanus* was

FIGURE 1 | Mean (\pm SE) abundance of (A) total (adults + pupae + larvae), (B) adult, (C) pupae and (D) larvae of *Echinothrips americanus* per treatment on different assessment dates. Treatments include the release of *Franklinothrips vespiformis* either alone or with supplementation of the cysts of the brine shrimp *Artemia franciscana* or no release of predators (control) in experimental cages containing sweet pepper plants. The predators were released on November 17 and 24. *Artemia franciscana* cysts were provided on November 17, December 2 and 14. Different letters denote statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$.

significantly reduced in the presence of *F. vespiformis*, regardless of the addition of supplementary food ($z = 1.09$, $p = 0.69$). Similarly, there was no significant difference in the abundance of *E. americanus* population between the control and the treatment adding *A. franciscana* cysts (741.0 ± 83.5).

Similar results were found for the adults of *E. americanus* ($\chi^2 = 148.53$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.0001$) (Figure 1B). Their abundance was significantly reduced at the end of the assessments in the treatments where *F. vespiformis* was released with (97% reduction

compared to the control; 13.6 ± 08 vs. 440.7 ± 35.1 adults) or without *A. franciscana* cysts (91% reduction; 40.0 ± 21.0). Finally, the abundance of pupae ($\chi^2 = 118.39$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.0001$) (Figure 1C) and larvae ($\chi^2 = 14.23$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.002$) (Figure 1D) was significantly lower in the treatments, where *F. vespiformis* was released, independently of the addition of *A. franciscana* cysts.

In the last assessment, we found an average (\pm SE) of $34.5 (\pm 4.5)$ and $29.3 (\pm 11.4)$ predator larvae in the *F. vespiformis* and *F. vespiformis* with *A. franciscana* cyst treatments, respectively.

5 | Discussion

Our results highlight the potential of *F. vespiformis* as an effective biocontrol agent against the leaf-dwelling thrips *E. americanus* in sweet pepper. *Franklinothrips vespiformis*, due to its leaf-dwelling nature, aligns more closely with the habitat of *E. americanus*, making it a potentially effective biological control agent. It is important to note the *F. vespiformis* effectiveness across all instars of *E. americanus*, including larvae, pupae, adults and eggs (Verachttert, unpublished). Thus, *F. vespiformis* might be a more suitable candidate for controlling leaf-dwelling thrips while *Orius* species are more appropriate against flower-dwelling thrips, such as *F. occidentalis*. Our findings are consistent with those of Schoeller, McKenzie, and Osborne (2022) who reported similar reductions in *E. americanus* populations by *F. vespiformis* on lima beans when supplemented with *A. franciscana*. This study further supports the potential of *F. vespiformis* as a valuable biocontrol agent. In addition, a recent study has shown that *F. vespiformis*, besides thrips, can also prey upon whiteflies (Schoeller et al. 2024) rendering it an interesting option for the control of other pests as well.

Adding *A. franciscana* cysts did not significantly improve the reduction of *E. americanus* populations compared to using *F. vespiformis* alone. As also suggested by Schoeller, McKenzie, and Osborne (2022), this lack of difference might be attributed to the experimental conditions, where the pest population was relatively high. The addition of *A. franciscana* could be more relevant in scenarios with lower pest populations or when releasing *F. vespiformis* preventatively. Further research is needed to explore how these dynamics change under varying pest densities and release strategies, whether curative or preventative, to better integrate *F. vespiformis* into IPM programs. Interestingly, in our study, the addition of *A. franciscana* cysts did not result in higher populations of *E. americanus*. As also shown by Vangansbeke et al. (2016), *A. franciscana* cysts are not an optimal food for the population growth of the thrips pest *F. occidentalis* but can serve as a suitable food source for predators like *F. vespiformis*, *Orius* spp. and phytoseiid mites.

Overall, our results demonstrate that *F. vespiformis* has substantial potential as a biocontrol agent of *E. americanus* in sweet pepper. We are currently performing more extensive field studies in commercial greenhouses to assess the inclusion of *F. vespiformis* in pest management strategies with other natural enemies like phytoseiid mites and *Orius* spp. in sweet pepper and other crops affected by leaf-dwelling thrips.

Author Contributions

Niel Verachttert: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, formal analysis. **Lien De Smedt:** conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, investigation. **Sten Boonen:** conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, investigation. **Apostolos Pekas:** conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

All authors work for Biobest Group N.V., which produces and supplies commercially *Franklinothrips vespiformis*.

Data Availability Statement

We confirm that the data supporting the results are archived Dryad with DOI <https://doi.org/doi:10.5061/dryad.2fqz612z1>.

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